

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD)

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases

Base 14 Crazy Sequential Representation

For example, two valid base 14 crazy sequential representations:

$$\begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{12217_{10} \quad 4649_{14}}} \\ -1_{14}/2_{14} * (3_{14} - 4_{14} + 5_{14}) ^ 6_{14} + 7_{14} * 89A_{14} + BCD_{14} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{302_{10} \quad 178_{14}}} \\ D_{14} - CB_{14} + A9_{14} ^ (8_{14} - 7_{14}) * 6_{14} / (-5_{14} + 4_{14} + 3_{14}) + 21_{14} \end{array}$$

For clarity, the corresponding base 10 representations:

$$\underline{\underline{-1_{10}/2_{10} * (3_{10} - 4_{10} + 5_{10}) ^ 6_{10} + 7_{10} * 1704_{10} + 2337_{10}}} \qquad \underline{\underline{13_{10} - 179_{10} + 149_{10} ^ (8_{10} - 7_{10}) * 6_{10} / (-5_{10} + 4_{10} + 3_{10}) + 21_{10}}}$$

Definition

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

$$\underline{\underline{1 \quad 2 \quad 3 \quad 4 \quad 5 \quad 6 \quad 7 \quad 8 \quad 9 \quad A \quad B \quad C \quad D \quad + \quad - \quad * \quad / \quad ^ \quad (\quad)}}$$

Digits 1 up to D occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$$\underline{\underline{-1/2 * (3-4+5) ^ 6 + 7 * 89A + BCD}} \qquad \underline{\underline{D - CB + A9 ^ (8-7) * 6 / (-5+4+3) + 21}}$$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$$\underline{\underline{-1/2 * (3-4+5) ^ 6 + 7 * 89A + BCD}} \qquad \underline{\underline{D - CB + A9 ^ (8-7) * 6 / (-5+4+3) + 21}}$$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$$\underline{\underline{-1/2 * (3-4+5) ^ 6 + 7 * 89A + BCD}} \qquad \underline{\underline{D - CB + A9 ^ (8-7) * 6 / (-5+4+3) + 21}}$$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$$\underline{\underline{-1/2 * (3-4+5) ^ 6 + 7 * 89A + BCD}} \qquad \underline{\underline{D - CB + A9 ^ (8-7) * 6 / (-5+4+3) + 21}}$$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$$\underline{\underline{-1/2 * (3-4+5) ^ 6 + 7 * 89A + BCD}} \qquad \underline{\underline{D - CB + A9 ^ (8-7) * 6 / (-5+4+3) + 21}}$$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$$\begin{array}{c} \underline{\underline{(1+2-3) * (45 * - (6^7) + 8 - 9ABCD)}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(DCBA98+7 * - (6^5) + 4) * (3-2-1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(1+2-3) * (45 / - (6^7) + 8 - 9ABCD)}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(DCBA98+7 / - (6^5) + 4) * (3-2-1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{(1+2-3) * (45 ^ - (6^7) + 8 - 9ABCD)}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(DCBA98+7 ^ - (6^5) + 4) * (3-2-1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{-(1+2+3) * (45 ^ (6^7) + 8 - 9ABCD)}} \qquad \underline{\underline{(DCBA98+7 ^ (6^5) + 4) * (- (3-2) + 1)}} \\ \underline{\underline{-(1-2+234 * (6 - (7+8-9))) * ABCD}} \qquad \underline{\underline{-(DCBA * (9 - (8+7-6))) * 543 - 2 + 1}} \end{array}$$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Aim

Identify genuine base 14 crazy sequential representations for 0000_{14} up to $DDDD_{14}$

Expected number of representations = $2_{14} + DDDD_{14} + DDDD_{14} = 20000_{14} = 76832_{10}$

Results

76824_{10} out of 76832_{10} were identified, see supplement.

Missing

Increasing	None
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Decreasing	91C1, 93A1, A3C7, B164, B5A4, B694, C014, C791
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Notes

Authors consider base 14 crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors did not simplify and/or optimize the crazy sequential representations.

Other Bases

Authors also identified genuine crazy sequential representations for other bases:

Date	Title
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

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